

Final Implementation of the Earth System Data Middleware Deliverable D4.3

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable provides the final implementation of the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) within the ESIWACE project. The developed middleware aims at deployment in both simulation and analysis workflows where the volume and rate of data lead to performance and data management issues with traditional approaches. A prototype has been coded, reviewed and agreed between the project partners. The source code for the middleware is tagged in Git as ESDM-V0.5, and it is available under LGPL license in a repository on Github: <https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>.

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) has been designed to deal with the fact that existing data libraries for standardised data description and optimised I/O, such as NetCDF, HDF5 and GRIB, do not have suitable performance portable optimisations for large-scale simulation workflows in climate and weather.

There are three broad data-related challenges that weather and climate workflows need to deal with, which can be summarised as requiring to handle:

- the velocity of high volume data being produced in simulations;
- the economic and performant persistence of high volume data; and
- high volume data analysis workflows with satisfactory time-to-solution.

ESDM provides a middleware architecture that delivers economical performance portability across different environments addressing these three challenges at once, which usually are independently considered by all major centres. The final product also aids the interests of stakeholders: developers have less burden to provide system-specific optimisations and can access their data in various ways. Data centres can then utilise the storage of different characteristics.

The prototype was documented and tested with I/O benchmarks on large scale systems to prove the feasibility of the design.

2. Conclusion & Results

An overview of the developed prototype for ESDM is as follows. From the application perspective, ESDM provides a data model that manages datasets in virtual containers with their metadata. Datasets are partitioned into fragments that are stored via various data backends. The middleware operates these data autonomously, i.e., decides on the storage backend and exposes characterisations of the data centres, that are then used by backend plugins to perform the fitting segmentation and distribution of data to storage objects and fragments.

The developed prototype, which has a refined architecture design from the previous Deliverable (D4.2), implements the following key features:

- provides relaxed access semantics, tailored to scientific data generation for independent writes;
- yields better performance via optimised data layout schemes;
- understands application data structures and scientific metadata;

- maps data structures flexibly to multiple storage backends with different performance characteristics based on site-specific configuration;
- separates file metadata operations from data access, which enables the exploitation of acceleration techniques. With traditional NetCDF and GRIB data, the relevant application metadata and much of the information about actual data layout is invisible to the file system (whether parallel or serial); and
- integrates with the NetCDF API as a subcomponent which allows applications to replace the standard NetCDF library with the ESDM supported library. By utilising standard tools belonging to the ESDM library, import/export files application between ESDM and NetCDF are now possible.

Additional prototypes for several components have been developed in the architecture. For the bottom layer, multiple data backends have been implemented, and a backend for POSIX allows the utilisation of parallel file systems. Furthermore, plugins for WOS and Clovis enable the use of specific DDN and Seagate storage. A decision-making component chooses how to partition datasets into fragments, and a scheduler runs background threads to perform the I/O. A configuration file allows defining the storage targets and the plugins to use, as long as setting the numbers of threads per node and the maximum quantity of parallel access.

A supporting metadata datatype library was developed to store arbitrary scientific metadata alongside the data, which is necessary for supporting NetCDF use cases. While the plugin for NetCDF was being implemented, the development of an HDF5 plugin was also explored. However, this idea was discarded for efficiency reasons. Metadata is stored at the moment by a POSIX plugin. The use of MongoDB and ElasticSearch as backends is being explored, and it will be provided shortly.

Testing and documentation are also part of the software deliverable. In that regard, auxiliary activities were conducted to cover the documentation of the installation procedure, including how to run the NetCDF benchmark, the utilisation of the test framework and the creation of Docker descriptions to support multiple distributions.

The prototype was deployed for testing on clusters of several data centres and systems: STFC (JASMIN), DKRZ (Mistral), CMCC (Athena and OphidiaLab), and SEAGATE (Test System). The execution of benchmarks demonstrated the feasibility of the design and the increased performance utilising multiple file systems together. As a specific example, with 200 nodes on DKRZ, a 25% performance gain over an independent I/O benchmark was possible. Performance evaluation was done with the performance tools in the current ESDM implementation, including the use of the NetCDF benchmark. Results have shown that Clovis, the API to access Seagate's Mero service, exhibits higher performance when using an asynchronous mode.

While a class of relevant use cases is supported, the prototype has some limitations that will be lifted in the future. For example, considering the mapping from data to storage locations, while some first steps were made with a performance model and automatic assignments, the current version uses a statistically predefined assignment according to a configuration file. Therefore, administrators of data centres are still required to do the final mapping. An example of improved decision-making that can be implemented is: store small and frequently accessed data on node-local storage while serialising multi-

dimensional data onto multiple storage backends. This simple idea can provide fault-tolerance and performance benefits for various access patterns at the same time.

The fundamental benefit of the ESDM design is that it provides the opportunity of a rich variety of future features without user intervention. In conclusion, the ESIWACE goals were achieved, and we realised that there is even more potential for our approach, which will be explored in project ESIWACE2.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	No
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	No
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The following contributions per partner have been made:

- Documentation (ESDM in general): UREAD, DKRZ
- ESDM core architecture: UREAD, DKRZ
- Backend plugin for Clovis: Seagate
- Backend plugin for WOS: CMCC
- HDF5 plugin (exploration): DKRZ
- NetCDF plugin: UREAD
- Metadata handling library (SMD): UREAD
- Testing and Evaluation: DKRZ, UREAD, CMCC, Seagate

The enclosed report contains relevant aspects of these contributions.

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6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is then general public.

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The main objective will be for the software to be used within weather and climate workflows. We intend that to be accomplished by explicit actions within the ESIWACE2 project.

7. The delivery is delayed: No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The initial plan was to develop the ESDM as a plugin for HDF5 (and hence support NetCDF via its internal use of HDF5). However, developing an ESDM plugin for HDF5 turned out to be significantly more time consuming than expected. After investing many months on the attempt during the project, we decided that this route should be discarded in favour of direct NetCDF integration. Doing so yielded additional flexibility in how the ESDM could be implemented, and how the ESDM API could be exposed, as well as reducing protocol switching overheads and the accompanying software. It did come at a cost in terms of reduced application (no longer supporting the wider direct HDF5 community). However, we believe that there are few, if any, direct users of HDF5 in our target community. On balance, we believe this change still delivers on our specific requirements and is consistent with a design philosophy of agility where possible.

Several advanced features have not been implemented in ESDM yet (primarily as a consequence of the initial attempt to use HDF5 using up time). However, this prototype was never expected to deliver all the functionality outlined in the design document (D4.2), and so the lack of these features is not a deviation from the project plan.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Sustainability is being dealt with explicitly as another project deliverable. However, the key sustainability goals for this software are to conform to (and extend) standardised APIs, and ensure the software is well documented, and easy to find and use. To that end, essential lessons are to exploit the API most

relevant to our community (NetCDF), rather than more generic APIs (at a higher cost in complexity), and to utilise GitHub with open development, rather than private repositories.

The modelling bears a lot of potentials to understand the cost-benefit factors and can serve as a discussion point between vendors and data centres but also between data centres and users. These models need the costs and performance characteristics as input and assume linear dependency between used variables which simplifies the situation (sometimes too much). But even so, determining the base characteristics such as costs for storage may be non-trivial when the procurement covers multiple components (storage + compute part of a supercomputer like for DKRZ).

Fine-grained models bear the difficulty to obtain the corresponding data needed for the simulation. In our case, obtaining the workload traces for tape access is non-trivial but shows that we have to increase the monitoring effort on the sites.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

Based on these results, we initiated a collaboration between Argonne National Laboratory and the company Kove to discuss cost-benefit of several storage-related architectures.

10. Full track of dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Organisation of a workshop	Understanding I/O Performance Behavior (UIOP)	22 March 2017, Hamburg (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/hamburg/2017/uiop	30
Organisation of a workshop	Exascale I/O for Unstructured Grids (EIUG)	25 September 2017, Hamburg (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/hamburg/2017/eiug	25
Organisation of a workshop	SIGIO UK	6 June 2018, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/_media/events/2018/sig-io-uk-intro.pdf	18

Organisatio n of a workshop	4th HPC I/O in the Data Center	28 June 2018, Frankfurt (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/_media/events/2018/hpc-iodc18-intro.pdf	40
Organisatio n of a workshop	Workshop on Storage Challenges in the UK	6 March 2019, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2019/sig-io-uk	35
Participatio n to a conference	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), Poster, "Modeling and Simulation of Tape Libraries for Hierarchical Storage Systems", Supercomputing 2016.	14-17 November 2016, Salt Lake City, (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	http://sc16.supercomputing.org/sc-archive/tech_poster/poster_files/post123s2-file3.pdf	100+
Participatio n to a conference	Julian Kunkel (DKRZ), Philipp Neumann (DKRZ), project poster ESIWACE at ISC 2017	18-22 June 2017, Frankfurt (DE)	Industry, Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.isc-hpc.com/id-2017.html	50
Participatio n to a conference	Jakob Luettgau (DKRZ), Poster, "Adaptive Tier Selection for NetCDF and HDF5", The International Supercomputing Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis	12-17 November 2017, Denver, (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://sc17.supercomputing.org/SC17%20Archive/tech_poster/poster_files/post214s2-file3.pdf	100+

Participation to a conference	Alessandro D'Anca (CMCC), Presentation, "Integrating Machine Learning Algorithms and HPDA Frameworks to Run Predictive Analytics on Large-Scale Climate and Weather Datasets", PASC18 Conference.	2 July 2018, Basel (CH)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1402496#.W36w3U	50
Participation to a conference	Jakob Luettgau (DKRZ), "Toward Understanding I/O Behavior in HPC Workflows", 2018 IEEE/ACM 3rd International Workshop on Parallel Data Storage & Data Intensive Scalable Computing Systems (PDSW-DISCS).	12 November 2018, Dallas (USA)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://www.doi.org/10.1109/PDSW-DISCS.2018.00012	80+
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), "Fighting the Data Deluge with Data-Centric Middleware", PASC 2019 Minisymposium: The Exabyte Data Challenge	12-14 June, 2019, Zurich, (CE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/_media/research/talks/2019/2019-06-14-fighting_the_data_deluge_with_data_centric_middleware.pdf	25
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), "Data-Centric I/O and Next Generation Interfaces", HPC IODC Workshop, ISC HPC 2019	16-20 June 2019, Germany (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/_media/research/talks/2019/2019-06-20-data_centric_i_o_and_next_generation_interfaces.pdf	50
Participation	Julian Kunkel	16-20 June 2019,	Scientific	https://hps.vi4io.org	50

Participation to a conference	(UREAD), "High-Level Workflows – Potential for Innovation? The NGI Initiative and More", BoF: Data-Centric I/O, ISC HPC	Germany (DE)	Community (Higher Education, Research)	/_media/research/talks/2019/2019-06-19-high_level_workflows_potential_for_innovation_the_ngi_initiative_and_more.pdf	
Participation to a conference	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), "The HPC Certification Program", BoF: International HPC Certification Program, ISC HPC	16-20 June 2019, Germany (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://hps.vi4io.org/_media/research/talks/2019/2019-06-18-the_hpc_certification_program.pdf	50
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (DKRZ), Presentation Towards new storage interfaces – chance or curse?, Workshop EIUG	25 September 2017, Hamburg (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342455#.W2wcVd-YXMU	25
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (DKRZ), Presentation, "Exploiting the Heterogeneous Storage Landscape in a Data Center", Per3S Workshop	12 January 2018, Rennes (FR)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342447#.W2waBt-YXMU	30
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (UREAD) Presentation "The Need for Next Generation Semantic Interfaces to Process Climate/Weather Workflows", SIGIO UK Workshop	6 June 2018, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342443#.W2wZKN-YXMU	18
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), Jakob Lüttgau (DKRZ) Presentation "Cost and Performance	28 June 2018, Frankfurt (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342440#.W2wYIN-YXMU	25

	Modeling for Earth System Data Management and Beyond”, HPC I/O in the Data Center Workshop				
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), “Community Development of Next Generation Semantic Interfaces”, joint morning session with the HPC-IODC and WOPSSS	28 June 2018, Frankfurt (DE)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342461#.W2wd49-YXMU	40
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), Presentation, “Challenges and opportunities for I/O”, GunHo Network meeting	4 July, 2018, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1342432#.W2wXWd-YXMU	30
Participation to a workshop	Julian Kunkel (UREAD), Presentation "Overcoming Storage Issues of Earth-System Data with Intelligent Storage Systems" at 18th Workshop on high performance computing in meteorology	25 September 2018, Reading (UK)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/learning/workshops/18th-workshop-high-performance-computing-meteorology	200
Participation to a workshop	Sandro Fiore, Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC) - HPDA & CoEs: ESiWACE Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe - EXDCI-2	16 May 2019, Poznan (PL)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/3242800#.XP7aJNMza1s	50

	workshop on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) during HPC Summit Week2019				
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	F. Mele, C. Palazzo, M. Mirto, A. D’Anca, S. Mocavero, S. Fiore, G. Aloisio (CMCC) - “The CMCC contribution to the ESiWACE project”, CMCC Annual Meeting 2018.	5-6 June 2018, Ugento (IT)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/record/1401154#.XQKAeqbYUko	100

Peer reviewed articles

These are the publications of those involved in this deliverable. These are inputs we upload in the European Commission database

Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	DOI	ISSN or eISSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Public & private participation	Peer review	Is/Will open access provided to this publication
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Toward Understanding I/O Behavior in HPC Workflows	https://www.doi.org/10.1109/PDSW-DISCS.2018.00012	(ISSN) 978-1-7281-0192-7	Jakob Lüttgau, Shane Snyder, Philip Carns, Justin M. Wozniak, Julian Kunkel, Thomas Ludwig	2018 IEEE/ACM 3rd International Workshop on Parallel Data Storage Data Intensive Scalable Computing Systems (PDSW-DISCS)	February, 2019	IEEE	IEEE Xplore	2018	64-75	No	Yes	Yes
Publication in conference proceeding/workshop	Cost and Performance Modeling for Earth System Data Management and Beyond	https://www.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02465-9_2	(ISSN) 978-3-030-02465-9	Jakob Lüttgau, Julian Kunkel	ISC High Performance 2018	Vol 112 03, 25 January, 2019	Springer, Cham	Lecture Notes in Computer Science	2019	23-35	No	Yes	Yes
Article in Journal	A Survey of Storage	https://www.doi.org/	(ISSN)	Jakob Lüttgau,	SUPERCOMPUTING	VOL 5,	Publishi		2018	31-58	No	Yes	Yes

	Systems for High-Performance Computing	10.14529/j sfi180103	231 3- 873 4	Michael Kuhn, Kira Duwe, Yevhen Alforov, Eugen Betke, Julian Kunkel, Thomas Ludwig	FRONTIERS AND INNOVATIO NS	no 1, 201 8	ng Cen ter of Sou th Ural Stat e Uni vers ity						
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Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Submitted	The Ophidia framework: towards HPDA at scale for climate change	S. Fiore, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, F. Antonio, A. D’Anca, G. Aloisio	HPC-IODC: HPC I/O in the Data Center Workshop	Yes
In preparation	Advanced Data Mapping and Performance with the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM)	Julian Kunkel, Bryan Lawrence, Luciana Pedro, Alessandro D’Anca, Cosimo Palazzo, Sandro Fiore, Paola Nassisi, Alessandra Nuzzo, Marco Chiarelli, Maria Mirto, Giuseppe Congiu, Huang Hua	PDSW/DISC Workshop	Green OpenAccess
In preparation	The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM): a portable architecture with optimisations for large-scale simulation workflows in climate and weather	Julian Kunkel, Bryan Lawrence, Luciana Pedro, Alessandro D’Anca, Cosimo Palazzo, Sandro Fiore, Paola Nassisi, Alessandra Nuzzo, Marco Chiarelli, Maria Mirto, Giuseppe Congiu, Huang Hua	Earth System Science Data (ESSD)	OpenAccess

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

No intellectual property rights resulted from this deliverable.

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CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

Final Implementation of the Earth System Data Middleware

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Abstract

This report provides documentation for the final implementation of the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) within the ESiWACE project. The developed middleware aims at deployment in both simulation and analysis workflows where the volume and rate of data lead to performance and data management issues with traditional approaches. A prototype has been coded, reviewed and agreed between the project partners. The source code for the middleware is tagged in Git as ESDM-V0.5, and it is available under LGPL license in a repository on Github: <https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>.

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) has been designed to deal with the fact that existing data libraries for standardised data description and optimised I/O, such as NetCDF, HDF5 and GRIB, do not have suitable performance portable optimisations for large-scale simulation workflows in climate and weather.

There are three broad data-related challenges that weather and climate workflows need to deal with, which can be summarised as requiring to handle: the velocity of high volume data being produced in simulations; the economic and performant persistence of high volume data; and high volume data analysis workflows with satisfactory time-to-solution.

ESDM provides a middleware architecture that delivers economical performance portability across different environments addressing these three challenges at once, which usually are independently considered by all major centres. The final product also aids the interests of stakeholders: developers have less burden to provide system-specific optimisations and can access their data in various ways. Data centres can then utilise the storage of different characteristics.

The prototype was documented and tested with I/O benchmarks on large scale systems to prove the feasibility of the design.

This document is the deliverable D4.3 from the Centre of Excellence in Weather and Climate in Europe (<http://esiwace.eu>).

1 Earth System Data Middleware

1.1 Introduction

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) has been designed to deal with the fact that existing data libraries for standardised data description and optimised I/O, such as NetCDF, HDF5 and GRIB, do not have suitable performance-portable optimisations for large-scale simulation workflows in climate and weather.

This text provides an overview of the developed prototype for ESDM. From the application perspective, ESDM provides a data model that manages datasets in virtual containers with their metadata. Datasets are partitioned into fragments, that are stored via various data backends. The middleware operates these data autonomously, i.e., decides on the storage backend and exposes characterisations of the data centres, that are then used by backend plugins to perform the fitting segmentation and distribution of data to storage objects and fragments.

The developed prototype, which has a refined architecture design from the previous Deliverable (D4.2), implements the following key features:

- provides relaxed access semantics, tailored to scientific data generation for independent writes;
- yields better performance via optimised data layout schemes;
- understands application data structures and scientific metadata;
- maps data structures flexibly to multiple storage backends with different performance characteristics based on site-specific configuration;
- separates file metadata operations from data access, which enables the exploitation of acceleration techniques. With traditional NetCDF and GRIB data, the relevant application metadata and much of the information about actual data layout is invisible to the file system (whether parallel or serial); and
- integrates with the NetCDF API as a subcomponent which allows applications to replace the standard NetCDF library with the ESDM supported library. By utilising standard tools belonging to the ESDM library, import/export files application between ESDM and NetCDF are now possible.

The significant benefit of the ESDM design is that it provides the opportunity of a rich variety of future features without user intervention.

1.2 Logical View: Data Model

The data model of a system organises elements of data, standardises how they represent data entities and how users can interact with the data. The data model can be split into three layers:

The Conceptual Data Model

Section 1.2.1 describes the entities and the semantics of the domain represented by the data model and the typical operations to manipulate the data. In our case, the scientific domain is NWP/Climate.

The Logical Data Model

Section 1.2.2 describes the abstraction level provided by the system, how the domain entities are mapped to objects provided by the system¹, and the supported operations for accessing and manipulating these objects. In short, the logical data model defines the semantics when using the operations to access and manipulate the system objects. For example, a system object of a relational model is a table – representing attributes of a set of objects – and a row of a table represents attributes of a single object.

The Physical Data Model

Section 1.2.3 describes how the logical entities are finally mapped to objects/files/regions on the available hardware. The backends of ESDM partly cover the physical data model, and the descriptions will stop at this level of abstraction.

1.2.1 Conceptual Data Model

Our conceptual data model is aligned with the needs of domain scientists from climate and weather. It reuses and extends the concepts introduced for a data model proposed by the Climate and Forecasting conventions for NetCDF data². This scientific data model consists of the following key entities:

Variable A variable, V , defines a set of data representing a discrete (generally scalar) quantity within a sampling domain, d . Whatever the sampling regime and dimensionality, values of a variable V will be laid out in storage. V is accompanied by

Metadata Metadata includes, at the minimum, a name (e.g. height, time), but may also include units and information about dimensionality, directionality, among others (e.g. degrees, months, days-since-a-particular-time-using-a-particular-calendar). This information may be inserted directly, e.g. via a (key, value) pair such as that necessary to expose $z = 1.5m$ for the air temperature at $1.5m$, or indirectly, e.g. via pointers to other generic coordinate variables which describe the sampled domain. Additionally, there may be a dictionary of supporting metadata which may or may not conform to an external semantic convention or standard. Such metadata could include information about the tool used to observe or simulate the specific variable. Additional metadata is also required for all the other entities described below.

¹An entity of the domain model such as a car could be assigned to one or several objects.

²“A CF Data Model and Implementation”, Hassel et al., 2017, GMD submitted.

Dimension The sampling domain d is defined by the dimensions, which also represents the coordinate axis. Dimensions will include metadata or details of how to construct an algorithm to find the exact sampling coordinates, perhaps using a well-known algorithm such as an ISO 8601 time.

Coordinate Coordinates are the set of values at which data is sampled along any given dimension. They may be explicitly defined by indexing into a coordinate variable, or implicitly determined by an algorithm. When we talk about coordinates, it is usually clear if we mean the N -dimensional coordinate to address data in a given variable or if we mean the coordinate along one dimension.

Cell The data values are known as points, which may or may not represent a cell. Cells are N -dimensional shapes where the dimensionality may or may not fully encompass the dimensionality of the domain. N -dimensional shapes can be implicitly defined as the Cartesian product of all dimensional coordinates forming the data cube of the cell. They can also be explicitly defined, either by providing bounds on the coordinate variables (via metadata) or by introducing a new variable which expressly represents the functional boundaries of the cell (as might happen in a finite element unstructured grid).

Data Set Variables can be aggregated into data sets. A data set contains multiple variables that logically belong together, and should be associated with metadata describing the reason for the aggregation. Variables must have unique names within a data set. Our conceptual model assumes that all variables are scalars, but clearly, the use of these scalars requires more complex interpretation.

Data Type The data type defines the types of values that are valid and the operations that can be conducted. While we are mostly dealing with scalars, they may not be amenable to interpretation as real numbers. For example, a variable may be storing an integer which points into a taxonomy of categories of land-surface-types. More complex structures could include complex data types such as vectors, compressed ensemble values, or structures within this system with their interpretation being handled outside of ESDM and documented in metadata. This feature allows ESDM to limit itself to simple data types plus arbitrary length blocks of bits.

Operators An operator defines the possible manipulations on the conceptual entities. The most straightforward operators will include `create`, `read`, `update` and `delete` applied to an entity as a whole, or a subset. However, even these simple operators will come with constraints. For example, it should not be possible to delete a coordinate variable without deleting the parent variable as well. There has to be a separation of concerns between operators which can be handled within the ESDM subsystem and those requiring external logic. Operators that require external logic include subsetting. ESDM will support simple subsetting using simple coordinates, but complex subsets, such as finding a region in real space from dimensions spanned using an algorithm or coordinate variable, may require knowledge of how such algorithms or variables are specified. Such knowledge is embedded in conventions such as the CF NetCDF convention, and this knowledge could only be provided to ESDM via appropriate operator plugins.

1.2.2 Logical Data Model

The logical data model describes how data is represented inside ESDM, the operations to interact with the data and their semantics. There are four first-class entities in the ESDM logical data model: **variables**, **fragments**, **containers**, and **metadata**. ESDM **references** may link ESDM entities, and a key property which emerges from the use of references is that an ESDM entity instance may not be deleted while references to it still exist. The use of reference counting will ensure this property as well as avoid dangling pointers. Figure 1.1 gives an overview of the logical data model.

Figure 1.1: Logical Data Model

Each of these entities is now described, along with a list of supported operations.

Variable In the logical data model, the variable corresponds directly to a variable in the conceptual data model. Each element of the variable sampled across the dimensions contains data with an associated data type. Variables are combined with both scientific metadata and technical metadata and are partitioned into fragments, each of which can be stored on one or more storage backends. A variable definition includes internal information about the domain (bounding box in some coordinate system) and dimensionality (size and shape), while the detailed information about which coordinate variables are needed to span the dimensions and how they are defined is held in the technical metadata. Similarly, where a variable is itself a coordinate variable, a link to the parent variable for which it is used is contained in the technical metadata. ESDM will not allow an attempt to delete a variable to succeed while any such references exist (see references). A crucial part of the variable definition is the list of fragments associated with it, and if possible, how they are organised to span the domain. Users

may choose to submit code pieces that then run within the I/O-path (not part within ESiWACE implementation). This operation covers the typical filter, maps and reduces services of the data flow programming paradigm. Fragments are created by the backend while appending/modifying data to a variable.

Fragment A fragment is a piece (subdomain) of a variable. ESDM expects to handle fragments as atomic entities, that is, only one process can `write` a fragment through ESDM and ESDM will `write` fragments as atomic entities into storage backends. The backends are free to partition these fragments further as appropriate, for example, by sharding using chunks. However, ESDM is free to replicate fragments or subsets of fragments and to choose which backend is appropriate for any given fragment. This feature allows, for example, ESDM to split a variable into fragments, some of which are stored on a parallel file system, while others are placed into the object storage.

Container A container is a virtual entity that provides views on collections of variables and allows multiple different data sets (as defined in the conceptual model) the access to the variables visible to ESDM. Each container provides a hierarchical namespace holding references to one or multiple variables and their metadata. Variables cannot be deleted while a container references them. The use of dynamic containers provides support for a more flexible organisation of data than a regular file system semantics. In addition, container efficiently support high-level applications such as Data Reference Syntax³. A container provides the ESDM storage abstraction analogous to an external file. Because many scientific metadata conventions are based on semantic structures, which span variables within a file in ways that may be opaque to ESDM without the use of a plugin, the use of a container can indicate to ESDM that these variables are linked even though ESDM does not understand why. Therefore, they cannot be independently deleted. When entire files in NetCDF format are ingested into ESDM, the importing tool must create a container to ensure such linking properties are not lost.

Metadata Metadata can be associated with all the other first class entities (variables, fragments, and containers). Metadata is split into internal ESDM technical metadata and external user-supplied semantic metadata. Technical metadata covers, for example, permissions, information about data location and timestamps. A backend will be able to add its own metadata to provide information to manage the data fragments from the storage backend managed by it. The metadata by itself is treated as a standard ESDM variable that is linked to the variable of choice. The implementation may embed (simple) metadata into fragments of original data (see reference).

Reference A reference is a link among entities and can be used in many places. References can be embedded based on the real data of these logical objects. For example, dimensions inside a variable can be references and a container typically uses references to variables.

It is crucial to notice that ESDM does not offer a simple hierarchical namespace for the files. It provides the primary functions to navigate data, teleportation and orientation, in the following fashion: queries about semantical data properties (e.g., `experiment=myExperiment`, `model=myModel`, `date=yesterday`) can be performed returning a list of matching files with their respective metadata. Iterating the list (orientation) is similar to listing a directory in a file system.

Note that this reduces the burden to define a hierarchical namespace for data sharing

³Taylor et al. (2012): CMIP5 Data Reference Syntax (DRS) and Controlled Vocabularies.

services based on scientific metadata. An input/output container for an application can be assembled on the fly by using queries and returning the resulting entities. As a container provides a hierarchical namespace, by harnessing this capability, one can search for relevant variables and map them into the local file system tree, accessing these variables as if they would be, for example, NetCDF files. By offering a FUSE client, this feature also enables backwards compatibility for legacy POSIX applications.

1.2.3 Physical Data Model

This section discusses the most relevant components and backends. They are ordered according to their position within the I/O stack from the top (application) to bottom (backend).

The scheduling component breaks down incoming `read` and `write` requests into subsequent requests to create or receive multiple fragments. The scheduler relies on a layout component to create a set of domain filling subrequests. In most cases, an application will not interface directly with ESDM, but through a standard frontend such as an HDF5 frontend. A POSIX backend allows interactions with parallel file systems. Besides data backends, also pure metadata backends, such as MongoDB, are possible, allowing the use of existing software stacks that typically reside in some storage backend.

Scheduling Component The I/O requests handled by ESDM are received via the ESDM interfaces. In most cases, these requests must collect additional information to identify multiple fragments to fulfil a request. The ESDM scheduler is responsible for progressing potential operations, coordinating requests, and invoking the appropriate handlers. In particular, the scheduler will consult the layout component to determine which fragments to create or use and which storage backends to choose.

Layout Component The layout component is responsible for finding a mapping to storage that takes into account information that is available through the conceptual and logical views of the data.

NetCDF NetCDF4 with Climate Forecast (CF) metadata and GRIB evolved to the de-facto standard formats for convenient data access for the scientists in the domain of NWP and climate. For convenient data access, it provides a set of features. For example, metadata can be used to assign names to variables, set units of measure, label dimensions, and provide other useful information. The portability allows data movement between different, possibly incompatible platforms, which simplifies the exchange of data and facilitates communication between scientists. The ability to grow and shrink datasets, add new datasets and access small data ranges within datasets simplifies the handling of data a lot. The shared file allows keeping the data in the same file.

Backend POSIX/Lustre Most of today's climate applications `read` from and `write` to parallel file systems such as Lustre. In this situation, a POSIX-like backend inside ESDM can handle `read` and `write` requests and organise the ESDM data structures.

Mongo DB A prototypical metadata backend is designed using MongoDB. This metadata backend scales horizontally with the number of servers, provides fault-tolerance, and its document model supports arbitrary schemas. Each type of object in the data model (container, variable, fragment) becomes a collection with indices on specific fields. Multikey indices allow indexing array fields such as the references.

Mero Backend Mero is an exascale ready object store system developed by Seagate and built from the ground up to remove the performance limitations typically found in other designs. Unlike similar storage systems (e.g. Ceph and DAOS), Mero does not rely on any other file system or raid software to work. Instead, Mero can directly access raw block storage devices and provide consistency, durability and availability of data through dedicated core components. Like Ceph Mero provides a key-value store component for small data and metadata and an object storage for raw data. The key-value store component in Mero can be used to keep track of containers, corresponding variables and shard inside them. For example, each container will be represented as an index in Mero. Every index will have references to all the contained variables. Variables are also described as indices and will contain variable metadata as well as references to shards. Shards, in this case, can be stored as different Mero objects or files in other storage backends.

WOS Backend The DDN WOS object storage solution represents a storage system architecture which manages data as objects, automatically storing files in the cloud in a geographically agnostic manner. Each object is stored with a unique OID that is used to retrieve the related data, delete them or verify the existence. The logical view for interactions between ESDM and Clovis/Mero is illustrated in Figure 6.28. To interact with the WOS cluster, DDN provides APIs for C++, JAVA and Python languages and an HTTP Restful interface. In particular operations such as `put`, `get`, `delete`, `exists`, `reserve` and `putOID` are allowed in blocking and non-blocking form.

1.3 Documentation

This section presents the documentation for ESDM (Section 1.3.1), ESDM applied to NetCDF (Section 1.3.2), three benchmarks (Section 1.3.3) and Docker instructions (Section 1.3.4) to run the system in different platforms.

1.3.1 ESDM

The following commands install ESDM in Ubuntu/Debian Systems.

```
# Download and install Git

apt-get install git

# Git clone ESDM directory from GitHub

git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm.git
```

```
# Install required packages

sudo apt-get install libglib2.0-dev libjansson4 libjansson-dev

# Install required packages
```

```
sudo apt-get install libtool libtool-bin

# Install required packages

sudo apt-get install automake cmake doxygen subversion

# Install required packages

sudo apt-get install mpi-default-bin libblacs-mpi-dev

# Install required packages (It may not be necessary.)

git clone git://git.sv.gnu.org/m4
```

```
# Build the project
```

It may be necessary to edit the file `prepare.sh` using `nano`, for instance. Just make sure the path for ESDM directory is correct.

```
cd esdm/deps

./prepare.sh

cd ..

./configure --prefix=$PWD/install --debug
```

```
# Run the project
```

```
cd build

make -j 4 install
```

File `_esdm.conf` has the configurations for the backends in ESDM.

```
Path: esdm/src/test

{
  "esdm": {
    "backends": [
      {
        "type": "POSIX",
        "id": "p1",
        "target": "._posix1"
      },
      {
        "type": "POSIX",
```

```
        "id": "p2",
        "target": "./_posix2"
    }
],
"metadata": {
  "type": "metadummy",
  "name": "md",
  "target": "./_metadummy"
}
}
```

1.3.2 ESDM-NetCDF

The following commands install ESDM for NetCDF in Ubuntu/Debian Systems.

```
# Git clone ESDM-NetCDF directory from GitHub
git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf.git
# Enter esdm-netcdf directory
cd esdm-netcdf/
# Update generated configuration files
autoreconf --force
```

```
# Build the project

It may be necessary to edit the file build.sh using nano, for instance. Just make sure
the path for ESDM directory is correct.
```

```
cd build/
./build.sh
```

```
# Run the project
make -j 4 install
```

Once the system is successfully installed, the following message should appear on the screen.

```

+-----+
| Congratulations! You have successfully installed netCDF! |
| |
| You can use script "nc-config" to find out the relevant |
| compiler options to build your application. Enter |
| |
|     nc-config --help |
| |
| for additional information. |
| |
| CAUTION: |
| |
| If you have not already run "make check", then we strongly |
| recommend you do so. It does not take very long. |
| |
| Before using netCDF to store important data, test your |
| build with "make check". |
| |
| NetCDF is tested nightly on many platforms at Unidata |
| but your platform is probably different in some ways. |
| |
| If any tests fail, please see the netCDF web site: |
| http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/ |
| |
| NetCDF is developed and maintained at the Unidata Program |
| Center. Unidata provides a broad array of data and software |
| tools for use in geoscience education and research. |
| http://www.unidata.ucar.edu |
+-----+

```

File `_esdm.conf` has the configurations for the backends in ESDM-NetCDF.

```

Path: esdm-netcdf/libsrcesdm_test/netcdf-bench

{"esdm":
  {
    "backends": [
      {"type": "POSIX", "id": "tmp", "target": "./_esdm",
        "performance-model" : {"latency" : 0.000001, "throughput" : 500.0},
        "max-threads-per-node" : 0,
        "max-fragment-size" : 104857600,
        "max-global-threads" : 0,
        "accessibility" : "global"
      }
    ]
  }

```

```
    ],  
    "metadata": {"type": "metadummy",  
                 "name": "md",  
                 "target": "./_metadummy",  
                 "accessibility" : "global"}  
  }  
}
```

1.3.3 Benchmarks

ReadWrite Benchmark Test

This test uses the ESDM high-level API to write a continuous ND subset of a data set. The source code is hosted on Github and can be found using the following URL:

<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm/blob/master/src/test/readwrite-benchmark.c>

```
# Go to the directory  
  
~/esiwace/esdm/src/test  
  
# Run the readwrite-benchmark file  
  
./readwrite-benchmark
```

```
# Output  
  
Write:  0.027s 2992.240 MiB/s size:80 MiB  
  
Read:   0.049s 1645.746 MiB/s size:80 MiB
```

NetCDF Benchmark

```
# Go to the directory  
  
~/esiwace/esdm-netcdf/libsrcesdm_test/netcdf-bench  
  
# Run the prepare.sh script  
  
./prepare.sh
```

```
# Run the test

./benchtool -f=esdm://longtest -w -r
```

```
# Output
```

		min	avg	max
benchmark:write	Open time	0.0012904980	0.0012904980	0.0012904980 secs
benchmark:write	I/O time	0.0283091750	0.0283091750	0.0283091750 secs
benchmark:write	Close time	0.0000326110	0.0000326110	0.0000326110 secs
benchmark:write	I/O Performance (w/o open/close)	1347.5126941171	1347.5126941171	1347.5126941171 MiB/s
benchmark:write	I/O Performance	1287.3449996970	1287.3449996970	1287.3449996970 MiB/s
		min	avg	max
benchmark:read	Open time	0.0001024170	0.0001024170	0.0001024170 secs
benchmark:read	I/O time	0.0671569910	0.0671569910	0.0671569910 secs
benchmark:read	Close time	0.0000061120	0.0000061120	0.0000061120 secs
benchmark:read	I/O Performance (w/o open/close)	568.0268292828	568.0268292828	568.0268292828 MiB/s
benchmark:read	I/O Performance	567.1103510780	567.1103510780	567.1103510780 MiB/s
DEBUG [0]	report.c:362	REPORT_END		

ESDM Metadata

This test checks the metadata APIs of ESDM. The source code is hosted on Github and can be found using the following URL:

```
https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm/blob/master/src/test/metadata.c
```

The test creates a file `mydataset.md` inside the container `mycontainer` with the metadata information. An example is:

```
mydataset.md

{"int":{"type":"j","data":3}}
```

ESDM Metadata for NetCDF

This test checks the metadata APIs of ESDM with NetCDF format. The source code is hosted on Github and can be found using the following URL:

```
https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm/blob/master/src/test/metadata\_nc.c
```

The test creates two files, `mydataset.md` and `myvariable.md` inside the container `mycontainer` with metadata information. Examples of these files are:

```
mydataset.md
```

```
"":{"type":"b","data":null,"childs":{"tech":{"type":"b","data":null},
"attr":{"type":"b","data":null},"special":{"type":"b","data":null}}}
```

```
myvariable.md
```

```
"":{"type":"b","data":null,"childs":{"tech":{"type":"b","data":null,
"childs":{"dims":{"type":"q2@g","data":[10,20]},"type":{"type":"c",
"data":"k"}}},"attr":{"type":"b","data":null,"childs":{"history":{"
type":"o","data":"This is some history"},"unit":{"type":"o","data"
:"Celsius"}}},"special":{"type":"b","data":null,"childs":{"vars":{"
type":"q2@o","data":["longitude","latitude"]}}}}}}
```

1.3.4 Docker

Docker is a set of coupled software-as-a-service and platform-as-a-service products that use operating-system-level virtualisation to develop and deliver software in packages called containers. The ESDM architecture was tested Using Docker to simulate Ubuntu 16.04 and Ubuntu 18.04. Installation for Fedora/CentOS/RHEL systems is expected to be completed soon.

A virtual operating system can be initialised with Docker using the command:

```
sudo docker run -it <operating system> bash
```

Ubuntu 16.04 and 18.04

Start with the following command to create a container for Ubuntu. Both tested versions have the same behaviour. Therefore, they will be included in just one section.

```
sudo docker run -it Ubuntu 16.04 bash
```

```
sudo docker run -it Ubuntu 18.04 bash
```

This operating system is now unspoiled. Therefore, additional packages have to be installed to enable ESDM to be tested.

```
apt-get update
```

```
apt-get install git
```

After this step, the procedures are the same described in Sections 1.3.1 and 1.3.2. For self-completeness, they are also included here.

ESDM

```
git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm.git

apt-get install libglib2.0-dev libjansson4 libjansson-dev

apt-get install libtool libtool-bin

apt-get install automake cmake doxygen subversion

apt-get install mpi-default-bin libblacs-mpi-dev

git clone git://git.sv.gnu.org/m4

cd esdm/deps

./prepare.sh

cd ..

./configure --prefix=$PWD/install --debug

cd build

make -j 4 install
```

NetCDF

```
# Git clone ESDM-NetCDF directory from GitHub

git clone https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf.git

# Enter esdm-netcdf directory

cd esdm-netcdf/

# Update generated configuration files

autoreconf --force

# Build the project

cd build/

./build.sh

# Run the project

make -j 4 install
```

2 Prototype Source Code for Earth System Data Middleware

2.1 Introduction

The ESDM is a middleware designed to allow interactions with different kinds of backends through data storing and retrieval. It is developed to exploit various specific plugins to enable connection and I/O operations on different storage types. The plugin infrastructure is embedded into a pre-existing and generic core module able to support and expose all the interfaces needed to define I/O operations on the different backends. Each specific plugin implements the interfaces to allow data management, storage, access and retrieval. The design targets, but is not limited to, earth system data, addressing the challenges faced by domain scientists and data centre operators for usability and performance. The architecture is built on top of HDF5 and NetCDF and utilizes scientific metadata to harness a data structure centric perspective while retaining well-established end-user interfaces.

This work collects final remarks regarding the open sourced prototype to test the ESDM concepts. The prototype includes backends for testing POSIX, WOS and Clovis storage services. In addition, the integration with HDF5 and NetCDF was started. However, given the complexity of the interfaces specified in the HDF5/NetCDF APIs, the implementations are not fit for benchmarking or tests with production applications yet.

2.2 Publication of the Source Code

The source code is hosted on Github and can be found using the following URL:

<https://github.com/esiwace/esdm>

Many open source projects entrust Github with their code because of its large existing user base and the community features to report problems and manage code suggestions by outside contributors. This choice was made to encourage collaboration from the HPC, climate and weather communities.

2.3 Architecture Overview of the Implementation

This section briefly summarizes the contents and the modules of the software prototype. Figure 2.1 provides an architecture overview that assumes the integration with NetCDF and HDF5 enabled apps. NetCDF 4 requires a minor patch to set the correct VOL plugin before

calls can be passed through to the ESDM Virtual Object Layer (VOL) Plugin. The HDF5 VOL Plugin, in turn, is responsible for mapping HDF5 abstractions to ESDM abstractions and vice versa.

Figure 2.1: Architecture overview of the planned system depicting the call path from applications through NetCDF/HDF5 to the ESDM.

Green components are in a stable state, and yellow components are work in progress. Components in dashed lines are part of the conceptual design, but the prototype implementation does not cover them at this stage. The backend plugins are discussed in Section 2.3.2.

2.3.1 Core

The ESDM core includes the following components:

- public Application Programming Interface (API) for containers, datasets, data spaces and metadata;
- module-system for data and metadata backends;
- configuration-system to load JSON-based site and backend configurations;
- preliminary implementations for the layout, scheduler and performance modules.

Figure 2.2: Components diagram to illustrate the interaction between components of the ESDM core and ESDM backends.

Figure 2.2 shows a component diagram of the ESDM core and how it interfaces with backend plugins. An application (HDF5 VOL plugin, for instance) interacts with the ESDM public API, and enqueue operations to the scheduler in an appropriated mode for the request (blocking or non-blocking). The scheduler consults the layout component which, in turn, examines the performance model and the site configuration to decide on how the request is being handled (e.g., split up, merged or distributed over multiple storage services).

2.3.2 Backends

The repository currently contains three backends that allow interfacing with systems based on POSIX, Mero/Clovis or WOS. The backends at this time are not complete, but provide essential (and sometimes unoptimized) **create**, **receive**, **update** and **delete** (CRUD) functionalities for metadata or data operations depending on the particular plugin backend type.

2.3.3 Frontends

The repository contains directories and tests for the planned frontends based on HDF5 and NetCDF. The initial plan was to develop the ESDM frontend as a plugin for HDF5 (and hence support NetCDF via its internal use of HDF5). However, developing an ESDM plugin for HDF5 turned out to be significantly more time consuming than expected and, therefore, this route was discarded in favour of a direct NetCDF integration. Doing so yielded additional flexibility in how the ESDM could be implemented, and how the ESDM API could be exposed, as well as reducing protocol switching overheads and the accompanying software.

The current implementation establishes the call path from an application to HDF5 and from HDF5 to the ESDM VOL plugin. The easiest route for using NetCDF from ESDM is setting the file `esdm://longtest` with the directive `-f`:

```
-f=esdm://longtest
```

2.4 Build Instructions for a Development Environment

Large parts of ESDM are built with standard tools available on most platforms. It is recommended to use Spack (<https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>) to build, manage and install dependencies. A step-by-step guide to set up a development environment is provided in the following.

```
# Download and enable Spack

git clone --depth=2 https://github.com/spack/spack.git spack
. spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh

# Set a gcc version to be used

gccver = 7.3.0

# Install dependencies

spack install gcc@$gccver +binutils
spack install autoconf%gcc@$gccver
spack install openmpi%gcc@$gccver gettext%gcc@$gccver
spack install jansson%gcc@$gccver glib%gcc@$gccver

# Load dependencies

spack load gcc@$gccver
spack load -r autoconf%gcc@$gccver
spack load -r libtool%gcc@$gccver
spack load -r openmpi%gcc@$gccver
spack load -r jansson%gcc@$gccver
spack load -r glib%gcc@$gccver
```

2.4.1 HDF5 with Support for ESDM VOL Plugin

Assuming all prerequisites have been installed and tested, a development branch of HDF5 can be built as follows.

```
# Ensure the environment is aware of dependencies installed using spack and dev-env

# Download HDF5 with VOL support

svn checkout https://svn.hdfgroup.org/hdf5/features/vol/
```

```
# Configure and build HDF5

cd vol
./autogen.sh
export CC=mpicc          # parallel features require mpicc
../configure --prefix=$prefix --enable-parallel
                    --enable-build-mode=debug --enable-hl --enable-shared

make -j
make test
make install
```

2.4.2 NetCDF with Support for ESDM VOL Plugin

Assuming all prerequisites have been installed and tested, a patched version of NetCDF to enable/disable ESDM VOL plugin support can be built as follows.

```
# Ensure the environment is aware of dependencies installed using spack and dev-env

# Download NetCDF source

version=4.5.0
wget ftp://ftp.unidata.ucar.edu/pub/netcdf/
      netcdf-$version.tar.gz
cd netcdf-$version

# Apply patches to allow enabling and disabling plugins

patch -b --verbose $PWD/libsrc4/nc4file.c
      $ESDM_REPO_ROOT/dev/netcdf4-libsrc4-nc4file-c.patch
patch -b --verbose $PWD/include/netcdf.h
      $ESDM_REPO_ROOT/dev/netcdf4-include-netcdf-h.patch

# Configure and build

export CC=mpicc
mkdir build && cd build
cmake -DCMAKE_PREFIX_PATH=$prefix
      -DCMAKE_INSTALL_PREFIX:PATH=$prefix
      -DCMAKE_C_FLAGS=-L$prefix/lib/ -DENABLE_PARALLEL4=ON ..

make -j
make test
make install
```

2.4.3 Building ESDM Prototype

Assuming all prerequisites have been installed and tested, ESDM can be configured and built as follows.

```
# Ensure the environment is aware of dependencies installed using spack and dev-env

cd $ESDM_REPO_ROOT

# Configure and build ESDM

./configure --enable-hdf5 --enable-netcdf4 --debug
cd build
make
make test
```

3 ESDM Interface for Mero via Clovis

Clovis is the Application Programming Interface (API) to access Seagate's Mero service and it can be used to manage Mero service, access objects (`read`, `write`, `create`, `delete`, etc.), and to perform index operations (key-value store operations). In this report, ESDM uses Clovis interfaces to access a Mero storage cluster.

Clovis APIs offer both synchronous and asynchronous modes. In synchronous mode, a Clovis application can submit a single object operation and wait for it. Multiple processes can be sent asynchronously (batch mode) and later wait for their completion. In between, Clovis application can do something else, e.g., computing interleaving I/O jobs.

Clovis is divided into the following sub-interfaces:

Access Sub-interface which provides a necessary abstraction to build the storage application;

Management Sub-interface which provides methods for the Mero cluster: deployment, configuration, re-configuration and monitoring;

Extension Sub-interface which allows applications to extend Mero functionality without modifying the core Mero.

Currently, the Clovis interfaces are written in C language, and the functionalities to access data on Mero have been implemented covering:

- Parsing configuration file to initialise the backend. Clovis applications need a list of parameters to access a Mero storage cluster such as the `confd` service network address, the client network address, the profile ID and process ID in the configuration. These parameters are stored in a configuration file, as part of the backend information. The Clovis backend parses the configuration and passes them to the Clovis initialisation interfaces.
- Connecting to Mero storage service with Clovis APIs. After the Clovis client instance has been initialised properly, the Clovis backend connects to the specified Mero storage cluster and fetches some essential information to initialise the client further.
- The following dataspace/dataset operations are now supported:

alloc A new object is allocated in Mero to accommodate dataset/data space. A globally unique object ID is generated and selected for the new object, an object ID along with some useful metadata are returned to ESDM if this operation is successful.

open Open an Mero object for `read/write`. While successfully opened, an opaque handle is returned for further access in `read/write` routines. This handle should

be closed with the `close` operation. All allocated resources will be freed. This handle should no longer be used.

read/write Mero objects can be read from and/or written to, with properly opened handle. Data can be read from and/or written to a specified location, with specified size. For read, a buffer to hold the returned data will be allocated within here and should be freed after use by ESDM.

close When a `read/write` operation has completed and the object is no longer used, the object should be closed.

- Fragment Retrieve / Update interfaces. Fragment update and retrieve are considered to be atomic operations in ESDM. These operations are implemented with the operations mentioned above. A fragment is identified by its container name, its dimensions and position. This information is used to form a unique fragment name. For every fragment, a new Mero object is allocated and associated. The mapping from a fragment to Mero object is managed and maintained and a fragment can be `open`, `read` and `write`, and finally `close`.
- Clovis backend finalisation. When all ESDM operations have been completed, the Clovis backend finalisation interface should be called to disconnect from Mero storage services and de-allocate all resources.
- A test utility is introduced to cover the above functionalities. The test utility is going to simulate ESDM access pattern and conduct operations with the described interfaces.

3.1 Performance Evaluation

Performance evaluation is conducted in a cluster consisting of eight I/O server nodes and eight client nodes to study the performance characteristics of the Clovis backend for ESDM. Six I/O server nodes have internal SSDs, and two other I/O servers have multiple HDD drives. These I/O servers are connected to client nodes with 40 Gbps Infiniband interconnections. Client nodes have dual Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz CPUs installed, and 128GB main memory. The application level performance is evaluated in both synchronous and asynchronous mode.

In this test, `create`, `read` and `write` are evaluated. In particular, `read` and `write` performance are the primary focus because these are the main I/O operations in the Clovis ESDM backend.

3.2 Synchronous Mode

Performance evaluation in this section is done with the performance tool in the current ESDM implementation: `src/test/readwrite`. The source code is hosted on Github and can be found using the following URL:

<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm/blob/master/src/test/readwrite.c>

This tool generates the user-specified size of data, writes the data as a fragment through the ESDM. ESDM flushes the data to the underlying data backend, which in this case is Clovis backend. Then the information is read back from the underlying backend and is compared with the original data. The following tests `write` and `read` the same amount of data for every process.

3.2.1 Single Node and Multiple Processes

The performance of the Clovis backend on a single node with multiple processes is shown in Figure 3.1. From the figure, we can infer that the performance scales nearly linear with the number of processes on a single node. The achieved performance is low, unexpectedly.

Figure 3.1: Aggregate `read` and `write` bandwidth on a single node.

3.2.2 Multiple Nodes and Single Process

The performance of the Clovis backend on multiple nodes with a single process is evaluated and shown in Figure 3.2. In this case, the performance also increases almost linearly with the number of client nodes. The unexpected low return, in both cases, is due to synchronous calling Clovis APIs and the unmatched chunk size. ESDM has to wait for a reply for every single I/O request. This is not an optimal way to make I/O requests. If the chunk size does not match the underlying parity group size, it causes extra internal `read-modify-write` requests which will also decrease performance. The next section evaluates the asynchronous mode of calling Clovis APIs and explains why it has better performance.

Figure 3.2: Aggregate `read` and `write` bandwidth on multiple nodes.

3.3 Asynchronous Mode

The current implementation of ESDM calls backend I/O interfaces, including Clovis APIs, synchronously. An additional experiment to evaluate the performance of Clovis applications gives us some baseline performance of a dedicated Mero cluster and the optimal bandwidth that an ESDM application may achieve if it also issues I/O requests asynchronously to the Clovis backend. The following results were achieved with the Clovis performance tool *m0crate*. For the next test, the I/O requests have the following parameters:

Parameter	Value
Unit Size	1MB
Stripe Size	8MB
Layout (PDRaid configuration)	8+2+2
I/O Request Size	128MB
Concurrent operations per thread	4
Number of Threads	8
Number of Objects to operate on	6

3.3.1 Single Node and Multiple Threads

The performance of the Clovis application issuing I/O requests in asynchronous mode is shown in Figure 3.3. In this experiment, the best performance is achieved when the number of threads is eight.

Figure 3.3: Aggregate `read` and `write` bandwidth on a single node and multiple threads.

3.3.2 Multiple Nodes and Multiple Threads

The test is expanded to multiple nodes, each one with eight threads. The result is shown in Figure 3.4. It can be noticed that when the Clovis application runs on eight nodes, the aggregate performance scales up. We can also see that when the number of client nodes increases to eight, the performance has only a factor of four improvement. This fallout is partly because of resource contention to I/O servers, and partly because of saturation of network bandwidth and/or disk bandwidth.

Figure 3.4: Aggregate `read` and `write` bandwidth with eight threads.

3.4 Performance Analysis

The performance values obtained in previous sections establish that Clovis applications using asynchronous mode have better performance. Servers can fulfil the multiple I/O requests delivered to Mero I/O servers asynchronously (batch mode) without waiting for replies, which increases the throughput dramatically. All Clovis applications, including ESDM Clovis backend, should consider using this feature.

In the testing, we tweaked various parameters with different values to discover which combination would yield the best performance. As a result, the following setting should be considered while developing Clovis applications, tuning their configurations, and deploying the storage clusters.

Parameter	Analysis
Unit Size	Matching the basic/minimum data size
Stripe Size	Matching the basic/minimum I/O size
Layout (PDRaid configuration)	Matching the I/O servers and disks
I/O Request Size	Bigger or equal than the stripe size and the offset should be aligned with the stripe size
Concurrent Operations per Thread	Matching the optimal value
Number of Threads	An optimal value determined by client CPU core and network bandwidth/throughput
Number of Objects	Matching the optimal value

Given a particular hardware system and Mero deployment, the unit size, stripe size and layout of objects have default settings. An application I/O request size should be carefully determined to match these settings. For example, the I/O request size should be one or multiple of a full parity group size. Otherwise, a full parity group is retrieved for a **read-modify-write**, or for a **read-verify** which will cause unnecessary data movement. The optimal concurrent operations per thread, number of threads and number of objects for compound I/O requests need to be tested when a given cluster is deployed.

When deploying the actual system, more I/O servers and more client nodes will yield better performance. Faster storage medium, like enterprise HDD, SSD, NVMe Flash, is critical for performance. Interconnection with higher bandwidth and throughput is also essential for overall performance. Clovis APIs can exploit high-speed networks, such as InfiniBand, benefiting the system bandwidth and throughput, and decreasing the delay of operations.

The performance model and characteristics can be analysed and tested for an ESDM Clovis backend. These performance numbers will be used in the scheduling policy for better overall throughput. This study will continue in the next phase of this project.

3.5 Performance Model

The performance of a system can be measured in different aspects. For a storage system, the performance may be measured in the following aspects (but not limited to):

- Single process (thread) **read** and **write** throughput
- Single node (with multiple processes/threads) **read** and **write** throughput
- Aggregate **read** and **write** throughput from multiple nodes (multiple processes/threads)
- Average delay of an **read** and **write** operation
- IOPS (**read**, **write**, **create** and **delete** operations per second)
- MTTF (Mean Time To Failure)
- High availability (expressed as a percentage of uptime in a given year)

In this document, we will work with **aggregate throughput** from multiple client nodes. The system performance can be tuned and optimised by various factors, such as device drives, network adaptors, CPU and memory of servers. For a specific system, these are planned and determined when the system is provisioned and deployed. There are also some tunable parameters, such as network buffer size in Mero and network switch configurations, which are tuned by system administrators, not requiring client users or applications intervention. Therefore, this section focuses on the parameters that can be determined and used by client users and applications considering asynchronous calls of Clovis APIs.

3.5.1 Tunable Client Parameters

Clovis applications **create**, **write**, **read** and **delete** objects. Objects have different parameters, such as unit size and layout (how the data of an object is distributed on devices). For every **read** and **write** operation of an object, the offset within the object and the length of the request determine where to do the **read/write** operation and how much data to be transferred. These two parameters, described as an [offset, length] pair, impact the final performance. If the offset of a **read/write** operation is aligned with the boundary of a stripe, and the length of such operation is a single or multiple of a stripe, the Clovis internal implementation has no need to do **read-modify-write** in the **write** case, or has no obligation to **read** extra units of data (not covered by this **read** request). From the application's point of view, there is no waste of data transfer. Clovis application should consider this as an essential performance optimisation while doing **read** and **write** operations. If this requirement is not satisfied, performance may drop considerably. Client application developers should understand their I/O pattern and then choose the object unit size correctly. They can also work with system administrators to define system-wide pool parameters and object layout.

3.5.2 Most Important Parameters

When we analyse the application performance of a specific system, the hardware and software system are already deployed and tuned. We only consider how to utilise the system to

achieve an optimised performance. In this sense, the most critical parameters for a Clovis application's aggregate performance are:

- Number of concurrent threads (or processes)
- Number of client nodes that applications can concurrently run on
- Number of servers that I/O operations can leverage

A simple performance model can be formulated considering these parameters.

3.5.3 Base Performance Calibration

The first step is to find and calibrate the base performance numbers for Clovis applications. The base performance is described as a Clovis application with a single process/thread running on a single node, doing **read** and **write** to a single Mero server. A Mero pool is a group of devices, nodes and, sometimes, racks. By defining and choosing different pools, Clovis applications can decide how to store their objects on different devices, different nodes and racks. This performance is denoted as P_b , which is characteristic of a specific system if other tunable parameters are defined and optimised. P_b can be evaluated when a system is deployed by using various performance benchmarks or performance utilities provided by Clovis.

3.5.4 Performance Model

From the performance evaluation results and the performance analysis, the anticipated aggregate performance of a Clovis application on a specific Mero system is formulated as the following:

$$P = P_b * (t * N_t + 1) * (n * N_n + 1) * (s * N_s + 1),$$

in which:

Parameter	Description
t	Coefficient for the number of threads to aggregate performance
n	Coefficient for the number of nodes to aggregate performance
s	Coefficient for the number of servers to aggregate performance
N_t	Number of threads (processes), starting from 0
N_n	Number of client nodes, starting from 0
N_s	Number of servers, starting from 0

The following analysis of the primary parameters justifies the proposed formulation:

Number of Threads From the test results, when the number of threads increases, the overall throughput increases almost linearly. However, when the number of threads exceeds

eight, the total performance drops, unexpectedly. As Clovis is limited by the CPU core, main memory, and other resources, when more Clovis instances compete against limited resources, this will bring more context switch, virtual memory allocation, swap and, sometimes, lack of available network buffers. All of these may be the reason for the damage in the overall performance.

Number of Client Nodes The maximal throughput increases along with the number of client nodes. However, when the client nodes exceed a specific amount (e.g. the number of Mero I/O servers), the aggregate throughput might not go higher because it has reached the up-limit of I/O server capacity of the network, or storage devices, or CPU capability. This result does not reflect a limitation to the number of client nodes that Clovis applications can concurrently run on. In many cases, the number of client nodes is much higher than the Mero I/O server nodes. Domain-specific applications using Clovis APIs to access Mero object storage run on customer planned client clusters, utilising CPU computation ability and data storage service. The aggregate throughput of the whole cluster may remain unchanged if up-limit is reached. However, Clovis application may have other benefits running on a large number of client nodes, e.g., computational resources.

Number of Mero I/O Servers The number of Mero I/O servers is limited by budget and by the requirements. In a typical Mero storage cluster configuration, objects are distributed across all I/O servers and on all device drives, increasing the overall performance and availability. By defining a customised pool configuration and choosing this pool when creating an object, the object can be stored only in a single Mero I/O server. This process is not an optimal way to store data; hence, it's not encouraged. So, the number of Mero I/O servers usually is the entire number of Mero I/O servers in a cluster.

In a real system, the number of threads, client nodes and servers start from one (hence the additional term plus one). From the above testing and experiences, the number of threads and the number of client nodes have a best-fit region limited by computer resources, such as CPU cores, main memory and network bandwidth. The number of threads has a best-fit region of $[1, 8]$ in our test cases. When client nodes are less than the upper limit, the overall performance is limited by client nodes and the number of servers nodes is not the bottle-neck. The number of servers in a real system is usually all the available servers in the system. The coefficients t , n and s are in the range of $[0, 1]$ and change accordingly to the initial conditions of setup. A well-balanced Mero cluster may have higher values of these coefficients. Optimization of hardware and software may also increase the base performance, as well as the coefficients.

Based on the experiments, the coefficients have the following values:

Parameter	Read	Write
t	0.190	0.074
n	0.570	0.530
s	1.000	1.000

As a specific example, in the test results in Section 3.3, the $P_b * (s * N_s + 1)$ for the **read** case is 300MB/s and for the **write** case is 369MB/s. These values are observed for our specific

setup in this test. Therefore, the coefficients of different Mero clusters may vary.

There are many other parameters for a Mero cluster, and they can also be optimised. When it happens, the coefficients may also change. These coefficients are just indicators of how the overall performance may change when the numbers of threads, client nodes and server nodes change. They are not an accurate measurement but a rough estimation. For an analytical model purpose in which initial conditions are not known, we can start the system with high-value coefficients. In a typical Mero cluster and typical use cases, Mero objects use a pool and a layout to distribute the data of objects to all available servers. In that case, $(s * N_s + 1)$ should be a constant value.

4 ESDM Interfaces for DDN WOS

The ESDM provides interfaces which allow the execution and management of I/O operations on different storage backends and architectures. The ESDM plugin for the DDN WOS backend is intended to lay out the structures required for WOS management and the functions enabling the initialisation and check of the remote backend connection as well as the read/write operations on the DDN WOS storage.

Considering that DDN allows the development of interfaces using C++, Java and Python programming languages and that the ESDM middleware has been implemented in C code, the development of a wrapper has been necessary to allow the interaction of ESDM with the underlying WOS storage. This module consists of a set of routines that individually match each one of the DDN WOS C++ native interfaces with the related ESDM API. Such routines have been collected in a specific C library that is part of the ESDM plugin for the DDN WOS backend.

4.1 ESDM Plugin for DDN WOS Implementation

As reported in Milestone M7 of the ESiWACE project ¹, the following functions have been implemented to provide mapping in C code with the native WOS C++ routines:

¹Check <https://zenodo.org/record/1453902#.XQ4Zr9-YU5k> for further information.

C Interface	WOS Library API	Description
Conn(char *host)	WosCluster::Connect(host)	Connect to the WOS cluster
GetPolicy(t_WosClusterPtr * wos, char *wpolicy)	wos→GetPolicy(wpolicy)	Check and get the wos policy
WosObjCreate()	WosObj::Create()	Create a WOS object
SetDataObj(const void *, int, t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj→SetData(data, len)	Set the data buffer to store in a wos object
SetMetaObj(const char *, const char *, t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj→SetMeta("<key>", "value");	Set the metadata (key, value) associated with the wos object
Put_b(t_WosStatus *, t_WosOID *, t_WosPolicy *, t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Put(status, oid, policy, wobj);	Store the wos object in the WOS cluster (blocking form)
Put_nb(t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosPolicy *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Put(wobj, policy, callback, context)	Store the wos object in the WOS cluster (non blocking form)
Get_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosObjPtr *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Get(status, oid, wobj);	Get the wos object from the WOS cluster (blocking form)
Get_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Get(oid, callback, context)	Get the wos object from the WOS cluster (non blocking form)
GetDataObj(const void **, int *, const t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj→GetData(data, length)	Get the data buffer from the wos object
GetMetaObj(const char *, char **, const t_WosObjPtr *)	wobj→GetMeta("<key>", value)	Get metadata from the wos object (key, value)
Delete_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Delete(status, oid)	Delete the wos object (blocking form)
Delete_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Delete(oid, callback, context)	Delete the wos object (non blocking form)
Exists_b(t_WosStatus *, const t_WosOID *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Exists(status, oid)	Check the existence of a Wos Object using its OID (blocking form)
Exists_nb(const t_WosOID *, Callback, Context, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Exists(oid, callback, context)	Check the existence of a Wos Object using its OID (non blocking form)
Reserve_b(t_WosStatus *, t_WosOID *, t_WosPolicy *, t_WosClusterPtr *)	wos→Reserve(status, oid, policy)	Reserve an OID to be used in the next PutOID call (blocking form)

C Interface	WOS Library API	Description
Reserve_nb(<code>t_WosPolicy *</code> , <code>Callback</code> , <code>Context</code> , <code>t_WosClusterPtr *</code>)	<code>wos→Reserve(policy, callback, context)</code>	Reserve an OID to be used in the next PutOID call (non blocking form)
PutOID_b(<code>t_WosStatus *</code> , <code>const t_WosOID *</code> , <code>t_WosObjPtr *</code> , <code>t_WosClusterPtr *</code>)	<code>wos→PutOID(status, oid, wobj)</code>	Put a Wos Object using the reserved OID (blocking form)
PutOID_nb(<code>t_WosObjPtr *</code> , <code>const t_WosOID *</code> , <code>Callback</code> , <code>Context</code> , <code>t_WosClusterPtr *</code>)	<code>wos→PutOID(wobj, oid, callback, context)</code>	Put a Wos Object using the reserved OID (non blocking form)

Finally, the interaction between the ESDM high-level functions and the routines above is enabled through the implementation of the following ESDM WOS specific interfaces:

Function	ESDM-WOS Interface
<code>init</code>	<code>esdm_backend_wos_init</code>
<code>open</code>	<code>esdm_backend_wos_open</code>
<code>write</code>	<code>esdm_backend_wos_alloc</code> <code>esdm_backend_wos_write</code>
<code>read</code>	<code>esdm_backend_wos_read</code>
<code>close</code>	<code>esdm_backend_wos_close</code>

Based on the routines mentioned above in C code, the ESDM plugin for WOS has been developed by implementing all the functions to allow the proper management of the WOS backend and the execution of the `read` and `write` operations. Specifically, the latter is managed through the provision of two interfaces by the ESDM core module, which deals with the I/O operations on fragments: `fragment_update` and `fragment_retrieve`. Hence, the implementation of the related WOS-specific routines, in particular, `esdm_backend_wos_fragment_update` and `esdm_backend_wos_fragment_retrieve`, has also been carried out. Such routines exploit the C++ WOS library at a lower level, which allows the final interactions with WOS objects, using the specific C code wrapper functions and the WOS interfaces as mentioned earlier.

4.2 ESDM Performance Model Implementation at CMCC

CMCC introduced an approach for dynamic performance estimation of backends to support the dynamic selection of the most appropriate storage backend in ESDM. The proposed schema assumes that a `write` time T of a fragment of L bytes can be obtained as

$$D + \frac{L}{S},$$

where D is the latency and S is the throughput. The estimator consists of a (periodical) execution of measurement of backend performance by writing two sample fragments with different sizes and processing the corresponding `write` times as follows.

Let L_1 and L_2 denote the sizes of two fragments and T_1 and T_2 be the corresponding `write` times. The current measures of throughput S and latency D are obtained as

$$S = \frac{L_1 - L_2}{T_1 - T_2}$$

with

$$D = T_1 - \frac{L_1}{S} \quad \text{or} \quad D = T_2 - \frac{L_2}{S}.$$

In the implementation of the proposed estimator, L_2 is a configurable parameter whereas L_1 has been set to $2 \times L_2$ for simplicity. In the case `write`, times T_1 and T_2 are nearly equal, mainly due to the erratic behaviour of the storage backend, network, etc., and then the measure is discarded.

Two modes have been implemented:

- single measure (available by default)
- multiple measures

In the former case, only one measure of backend performance is taken. In particular, the estimator is called during the plugin initialisation phase. In the latter case, a specific thread, created and started during the plugin initialisation phase, periodically takes new measures and updates a smoother estimation for throughput and latency using an exponential weight average (first-order low-pass filter). The period between two consecutive tests and the filter weight are configurable parameters.

The core module of this schema includes the following functions:

```
int esdm_backend_parse_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp
(json_t * perf_model_str,
 esdm_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp_t * out_data);
```

This function loads the module configuration parameters. They are stored as JSON object as in the following example.

```

{
    latency : 0.0000001,    // (sec) Initial estimation of latency, set manually
    throughput : 10000.0,  // (MB/s) Initial estimation of throughput, set manually
    size : 1048576,        // (bytes) Size of the fragment used for measurements
    period : 10.0,         // (sec) Period between two measurements (see below)
    alpha : 0.5            // Filter weight (see below)
}

```

```

int esdm_backend_start_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp
(esdm_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp_t * data,
 esdm_backend * backend,
 int (*checker)(esdm_backend *, int, float *));

```

This function starts the estimator. It makes use of the plugin-dependent function `checker` to actually write sample fragments and take the corresponding `write` times.

```

int esdm_backend_update_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp
(esdm_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp_t* data);

```

This function updates the values of the estimated throughput and latency with a new measurement.

```

int esdm_backend_estimate_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp
(esdm_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp_t * data,
 esdm_fragment_t * fragment, float *out_time);

```

This function returns the `write` time estimation of the input fragment.

```
int esdm_backend_get_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp
(esdm_dynamic_perf_model_lat_thp_t* data, char **json);
```

This function returns a JSON object with the current estimation of throughput and latency. The ESDM core modules can call this function during library finalisation to save the last performance estimation for each backend. This estimation could thus improve the initial estimate for the next times. A function to **write** testing fragments and get I/O times is needed to use this module for each plugin.

```
int wos_backend_performance_check
(esdm_backend *eb, int data_size, float *out_time);
```

This function is the implementation of the function **checker** (introduced above) specific for the ESDM plugin developed for the management of I/O operations on the DDN WOS cluster. As stated before this function writes sample fragments over WOS cluster and take the corresponding **write** times.